

A novel and facile environmentally benign oxidative electrocyclicization of acylthiosemicarbazone into biodynamic 1,3,4-oxadiazoles[†]

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Abstract : A novel, facile and green oxidative electrocyclicization of the acylthiosemicarbazone into 5-substituted-2-amino(substituted)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles at platinum electrode using acetonitrile as non-aqueous solvent and lithium perchlorate as supporting electrolyte at an apparent current density of 4-6 F/mol is described. The electrooxidative cyclization was carried out under controlled potential electrolysis in an undivided cell. The reaction was smooth and quantitative with excellent yield. The antifungal screening of the synthesized compounds was also done against *Alternaria solani*, *Fusarium oxisporum-udum* and *Aspergillus niger* species.

Keywords : Electrooxidation, controlled potential electrolysis, supporting electrolyte, oxadiazole, antifungal, acylthiosemicarbazone, platinum electrode, green chemistry.

Introduction

1,3,4-Oxadiazoles exhibit diverse pharmaceutical properties¹⁻⁷. Development of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles as insecticidal⁸, antibacterial⁹, antifungal¹⁰, antimicrobial⁵⁻⁷, antituberculosic¹¹, anti-HIV⁵, anticancer¹², muscle relaxant¹³, anti-inflammatory¹⁴ and analgesic¹⁵ agent has renewed interest in synthesis and synthetic manipulation of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles. Due to increasing awareness of environmental pollution and legislation for protection of environment, there has been greater emphasis on ecofriendly organic transformations. Recently electroorganic reactions have attracted attention because the process is ecofriendly as well as it is associated with milder reaction conditions, enhancement of yield, high selectivity and considerable reduction in reaction time which are additional attributes, to green chemistry.

As part of our programme for the development of simple, facile, environmentally benign protocol for the synthesis of biodynamic heterocyclic compounds, we describe here for the oxidative electrocyclicisation of acylthiosemicarbazone into 5-substituted-2-amino (substituted)-1,3,4-oxadiazole and evaluation of their antifungal activity.

Results and discussion

It has been found in the literature study that the methods for synthesis of oxadiazole **4** include bromine oxidation of semicarbazide derivative and the cyclodesulfurization of acylthiosemicarbazide derivatives in the solution using I₂/NaOH or 1,3-dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC)¹⁶⁻¹⁹ as well as mercury(II) acetate (Hg(OAc)₂) or yellow mercury(II)oxide HgO²⁰⁻²². Evans,²³ synthesized oxadiazole derivatives by rapid parallel synthesis in efficient one-pot preparation using resin-bound reagents. All these methods are usually carried out in various different synthetic steps and require the heating at higher temperature. The handling of these reagents is not only difficult but also very hazardous to environment. The each stage of the reaction including extraction and purification of the products from the mixture requires great precautions.

The objective of our research programme is to find out new general ecofriendly efficient synthetic method²⁴⁻²⁸ for the preparation of important organic compounds in which the use of toxic reagents could be minimized or eliminated. To fulfill our objective, an effort was made as a trial for the electrooxidation of acylthiosemicarbazone

[†]In honour of Professor Padmakar V. Khadikar.

3 obtained by reacting acylhydrazine **1** with isothiocyanates **2** and to our surprise we got success in the oxidation of acylthiosemicarbazone **3** into 5-substituted-2-amino(substituted)-1,3,4-oxadiazole. In the oxidation, non-aqueous solvent acetonitrile and lithium perchlorate (LiClO_4) as supporting electrolyte were used. Non toxic nature of acetonitrile, LiClO_4 and their easy handling has additional attributes to the process.

one anodic peak corresponding to one electron oxidation of acylthiosemicarbazone to product **4d**.

Acylthiosemicarbazone **3** involves transfer of a proton from N atom to the S atom of thioenol and forms an enolate ion **3a** which on one electron oxidation gave a free radical **3b**. Free radical **3b** on subsequent one electron reduction gave carbon free radical **3d** which on radical coupling followed by dehydrosulphidation results in

Scheme 1

All the electrolysis experiments were carried out at their corresponding oxidation potentials and were completed in 3 to 5 h. The current potential data was recorded at the interval of 15 min (Table 1). Approximately 4 F/mol of electricity was passed for the electrolysis which is very small in comparison to energy used in other conventional methods.

CV studies (Fig. 1) have shown that the process is one electron oxidation process. Cyclic voltogram exhibited

the formation of **4** (Scheme 2) in 80–95% yield. Aromatic stabilization is the driving force behind the elimination of hydride ion. Electron releasing nature of R' was found to enhance the dropping of hydride ion (H^-) and the formation of aromatic system. That the process involves dehydrosulphidation, was supported by the confirmation of evolution of H_2S by lead acetate paper.

In summary, we carried out successfully anodic synthesis of 5-substituted-2-amino(1,3,4-

Fig. 1. Fig. 1 represents the cyclic voltogram obtained from a 0.01 M solution of LiClO_4 . The corresponding voltogram exhibits one anodic peak at 1.44 E/mV as the reference electrode. This peak corresponds to the oxidation of acylthiosemicarbazone to the product.

Scheme 2

oxadiazole in acetonitrile containing LiClO₄ by constant potential electrolysis. The electro-oxidative cyclisation in this selective and efficient electrolytic system seems to be promising since the synthesis of oxadiazole derivatives can be carried out under safe conditions without hazardous reagents.

Experimental

All melting points were recorded on an electrothermal apparatus and were uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu 8201 PC IR spectrophotometer (4000–400 cm⁻¹) in KBr pellets and reported in cm⁻¹. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were obtained on Bruker DRX 300 MHz FT spectrometer instruments in a deuteriochloroform (CDCl₃) solution using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard. Cyclic voltammetry was performed using ALSCH instruments Electrochemical analyzer Model 600A. Mass spectra were obtained by EI method with Shimadzu GCMS-QP5050A. High resolution spectra were obtained on JEOL-700 Mass spectrometer operating at 70 eV. Preparative electrolysis were carried out using a Hokutodenko potentiostat/galvanostat HA-501.

All the compounds, acetonitrile, phenylisothiocyanate, mercury, KCl and chloroform were of AnalaR grade. Water used for the experiments was double distilled.

Preparation of acylthiosemicarbazone (3) : The acylthiosemicarbazone (3) was prepared by using standard procedure. The equimolar amount of acylhydrazine (1) and phenylisothiocyanate (2) were mixed in a small beaker with continuous stirring. After few minutes of stirring, the mixture was left overnight which gave acylthiosemicarbazone as a solid.

General procedure of anodic cyclization of acylthiosemicarbazone (3) :

Acylthiosemicarbazone (3) (0.271 g, 1.0 mmol), lithium perchlorate (0.16 g, 1.0 mmol) and acetonitrile (100 ml) was taken in 250 ml three-electrode cell assembly with platinum plate (flattened sheet of dimension 1.0 cm × 1.0 cm) as working as well as counter electrode and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode²⁹⁻³¹. Magnetic stirrer was used for the proper mixing of reaction mixture. Preparative scale controlled potential electrolysis³²⁻³⁴ (1.45 E/mV vs SCE) were performed at their oxidation potentials at room temperature. The current-potential data given in the Table 1 was recorded with the help of potential cum galvanostat. Approximately 4.5–6.0 F/mol of electricity was passed for the electrolysis.

Initially 15 F/mol current density and only acetonitrile as non-aqueous solvent was used and then current

Table 1. Current-potential data of electroorganic synthesis of 1,3,4-oxadiazole

Entry	R ¹	R ²	Applied potential (E/mV)	Current density (i/Acm ⁻²)
4a	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	1440	0.04
4b	C ₆ H ₅ -	<i>m</i> -H ₃ C-C ₆ H ₄ -	1430	0.06
4c	CH ₃ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	1420	0.05
4d	CH ₃ -	<i>p</i> -H ₃ CO-C ₆ H ₄ -	1440	0.08
4e	<i>p</i> -HO-C ₆ H ₄ -	<i>p</i> -H ₃ C-C ₆ H ₄ -	1420	0.05
4f	<i>p</i> -HO-C ₆ H ₄ -	<i>m</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	1430	0.03
4g	C ₁₇ H ₃₅ -	<i>o</i> -H ₃ CO-C ₆ H ₄ -	1470	0.05
4h	C ₁₇ H ₃₅ -	<i>o</i> -H ₃ C-C ₆ H ₄ -	1260	0.08
4i	CH ₃ COCH ₂ -	<i>m</i> -H ₃ C-C ₆ H ₄ -	1300	0.09
4j	CH ₃ COCH ₂ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	1430	0.04
4k	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₂ -	<i>p</i> -H ₃ C-C ₆ H ₄ -	1430	0.08
4l	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₂ -	<i>p</i> -H ₃ CO-C ₆ H ₄ -	1420	0.05

density of 10 F/mol, 6 F/mol and 4 F/mol was used. It was found that reaction proceeded smoothly and quantitatively at an apparent current density of 4 F/mol but the time required for oxidation was about 5–10 h. However, by adding supporting electrolyte LiClO₄, reactant was transformed into product in 3 to 5 h. So, the electrocyclization was carried out in acetonitrile at an apparent current density of 4.5–6.0 F/mol using LiClO₄ as a supporting electrolyte which is very small in comparison to energy used in other conventional methods. Progress of reaction was monitored by TLC. All the products were solid and coloured. After electrolysis, the supporting electrolyte was removed by silica gel column chromatography. The products were isolated by silica gel column chromatography (CHCl₃ : H₂O, 1 : 1 v/v).

5-Phenyl-2-(phenylamino)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4a) : Dark yellowish needle, yield 90%, molecular formula C₁₄H₁₁N₃O, mol. wt. 237; IR (KBr) : 2868.0, 3261.0, 1160.0, 1580.0 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃/3000 MHz) : δ 6.46–7.48 (10H, m), 7.75 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 115–146, 164; Anal. calcd. : C, 70.87; H, 4.67; N, 17.71. Found : C, 70.85; H, 4.65; N, 17.69; MS calcd. *m/z* 237.0902; found : *m/z* 237.0906.

5-Phenyl-2-(*m*-methylphenylamino)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4b) : Dark brownish needle, yield 92%, molecular formula C₁₅H₁₃N₃O, mol. wt. 251; IR (KBr) : 1180.0,

1565.0, 2870.0, 3220.0 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃/3000 MHz) : δ 2.35 (3H, s), 7.22–7.48 (5H, m), 6.26–6.89 (4H, m), 7.75 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃/3000 MHz) : δ 13.7, 112.0–146.0, 127.0–136.0, 164.0; Anal. calcd. : C, 71.71; H, 5.21; N, 16.72. Found : C, 71.67; H, 5.18; N, 16.70; MS calcd. : *m/z* 251.1059; found : *m/z* 251.1061.

5-Methyl-2-(phenylamino)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4c) : Dark brownish needle, yield 90%, molecular formula C₉H₉N₃O, mol. wt. 175; IR (KBr) : 1150.0, 1550.0, 2855.0, 3336.0 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃/3000 MHz) : δ 2.35 (3H, s), 6.46–7.01 (5H, m), 7.75 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃/3000 MHz) : δ 13.7, 115.0–146.0, 164.0; Anal. calcd. : C, 61.70; H, 5.18; N, 23.99. Found : C, 61.68; H, 5.17; N, 23.96; MS calcd. : *m/z* 175.0749; found : *m/z* 175.0746.

5-Methyl-2-(*p*-methoxyphenylamino)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4d) : Dark brownish needle, yield 95%, molecular formula C₁₀H₁₁N₃O₂, mol. wt. 205; IR (KBr) : 1112.2, 1544.4, 2856.0, 3444.0 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃/3000 MHz) : δ 2.35 (3H, s), 3.73 (3H, s), 6.35–6.52 (4H, m), 7.75 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃/3000 MHz) : δ 56.0, 13.7, 114.9–139.0, 164.0, 170.0; Anal. calcd. : C, 61.70; H, 5.18; N, 23.99. Found : C, 61.68; H, 5.17; N, 23.96; MS calcd. : *m/z* 205.0851; found : *m/z* 205.0849.

5-*p*-Hydroxyphenyl-2-(*p*-methylphenylamino)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4e) : Dark brownish needle, yield 88%, molecular formula C₁₅H₁₃N₃O₂, mol. wt. 267; IR (KBr) : 1160.0, 1570.0, 3350.0, 2860.0 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃/3000 MHz) : δ 2.35 (3H, s), 6.34–7.31 (8H, m), 7.75 (1H, s), 2.00 (1H, s, exchangeable with D₂O); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃/3000 MHz) : δ 13.7, 115.0–157.3, 164.0; Anal. calcd. : C, 67.40; H, 4.90; N, 15.72. Found : C, 67.38; H, 4.87; N, 15.70; MS calcd. : *m/z* 267.1008; found : *m/z* 267.1016.

5-*p*-Hydroxyphenyl-2-(*m*-chlorophenylamino)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4f) : Dark brownish needle, yield 85%, molecular formula C₁₄H₁₀N₃O₂Cl, mol. wt. 287.5; IR (KBr) : 1160.0, 1570.0, 3350.0, 2860.0 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃/3000 MHz) : δ 6.34–7.31 (8H, m), 7.75 (1H, s), 2.00 (1H, s, exchangeable with D₂O); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃/3000 MHz) : δ 115.0–157.0, 164.0; Anal. calcd. : C,

58.45; H, 3.50; Cl, 12.32; N, 14.61. Found : C, 58.43; H, 5.17; N, 3.47; Cl, 12.30; N, 14.59; MS calcd. : m/z 287.0462; found : m/z 287.0468.

5-Heptadecyl-2-(o-methoxyphenylamino)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4g) : Dark brownish needle, yield 65%, molecular formula $C_{26}H_{43}N_3O_2$, mol. wt. 429; IR (KBr) : 1160.0, 1580.0, 2868.0, 3261.0 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3/3000$ MHz) : δ 2.35 (3H, s), 3.73 (3H, s), 6.35–6.57 (4H, m), 1.29–1.33 (32H, br s), 7.75 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3/3000$ MHz) : δ 56.0, 13.7, 132.0–148.0, 30.3, 164.0; Anal. calcd. : C, 72.68; H, 10.09; N, 9.78. Found : C, 72.65; H, 10.07; N, 9.75; MS calcd. : m/z 429.3355; found : m/z 429.3416.

5-Heptadecyl-2-(o-methylphenylamino)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4h) : Dark brownish needle, yield 62%, molecular formula $C_{26}H_{43}N_3O$, mol. wt. 413; IR (KBr) : 1165.0, 1580.0, 2975.0, 3315.0 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3/3000$ MHz) : δ 2.35 (3H, s), 6.34–6.82 (4H, m), 1.29–1.33 (32H, br s), 7.75 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3/3000$ MHz) : δ 13.7, 118.0–147.0, 23.1–32.1, 164.0; Anal. calcd. : C, 75.50; H, 10.48; N, 10.16. Found : C, 75.48; H, 10.45; N, 10.14; MS calcd. : m/z 413.3406; found : m/z 413.3416.

5-(2-Oxopropyl)-2-(m-methylphenylamino)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4i) : Dark brownish needle, yield 87%, molecular formula $C_{12}H_{13}N_3O_2$, mol. wt. 231; IR (KBr) : 1165.0, 1580.0, 2975.0, 3315.0 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3/3000$ MHz) : δ 2.35 (3H, s), 3.71 (2H, s), 6.34–6.81 (4H, m), 3.73 (3H, s), 7.75 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3/3000$ MHz) : δ 13.7, 43.0, 115.0–147.0, 56.0, 164.0; Anal. calcd. : C, 62.33; H, 5.67; N, 18.17. Found : C, 62.30; H, 5.65; N, 18.15; MS calcd. : m/z 231.2505; found : m/z 231.2508.

5-(2-Oxopropyl)-2-(phenylamino)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4j) : Dark brownish needle, yield 85%, molecular formula $C_{11}H_{11}N_3O_2$, mol. wt. 217; IR (KBr) : 2868.0, 3261.0, 1160.0, 1580.0 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3/3000$ MHz) : δ 6.46–7.01 (5H, m), 3.71 (2H, s), 3.73 (3H, s), 7.75 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3/3000$ MHz) : δ 115.0–146.7, 43.0, 164.0; Anal. calcd. : C, 60.82; H, 5.10; N, 19.34. Found : C, 60.80; H, 5.80; N, 19.32; MS calcd. : m/z 217.0851;

found : m/z 217.0849.

5-Tridecyl-2-(p-methylphenylamino)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4k) : Dark brownish needle, yield 70%, molecular formula $C_{22}H_{35}N_3O$, mol. wt. 357; IR (KBr) : 1155.0, 1560.0, 2860.0, 3261.0 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3/3000$ MHz) : δ 2.35 (3H, s), 3.73 (3H, s), 6.34–6.84 (4H, m), 1.33–2.55 (24H, br s), 7.75 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3/3000$ MHz) : δ 56.0, 115.0–143.7, 30.0–32.5; Anal. calcd. : C, 73.91; H, 9.87; N, 11.75. Found : C, 73.87; H, 9.85; N, 11.73; MS calcd. : m/z 357.2780; found : m/z 357.2777.

5-Tridecyl-2-(p-methoxyphenylamino)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4l) : Dark brownish needle, yield 75%, molecular formula $C_{22}H_{35}N_3O_2$, mol. wt. 373; IR (KBr) : 1157.0, 1570.0, 3325.0, 2868.0 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3/3000$ MHz) : δ 2.35 (3H, s), 3.39 (3H, s), 6.35–6.52 (4H, m), 1.29–2.55 (24H, br s), 7.75 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3/3000$ MHz) : δ 56.0, 13.7, 114.9–139.0, 30.0–32.5; Anal. calcd. : C, 70.74; H, 9.44; N, 11.25. Found : C, 70.72; H, 9.42; N, 11.23; MS calcd. : m/z 373.2729; found : m/z 373.2731.

Antifungal screening

The antifungal screening of the compounds **4a-l** was carried out against *Fusarium oxysporum-udum*, *Alternaria solani* and *Aspergillus niger* by agar growth technique³⁵ at 10, 100, 1000 ppm concentration using commercial fungicide, Griseofulvin and Dithane M-45 as standards. The number of replicate assays in each were three, and six replicate controls were used. No remarkable morphological changes were observed in the developing fungi. The test fungi were inoculated in the centre of the petridishes and incubated at 28 ± 1 °C for 96 h. After this time the percent inhibition of the mycelia growth compared with that in control dishes was recorded. Most of the screened compounds showed promising fungicidal activity at 1000 ppm concentration with both the test fungi *Fusarium oxysporum-udum*, *Alternaria solani* and *Aspergillus niger* (Table 2). Among the tested compounds, **4d**, **4g** and **4l** displayed fungicidal action comparable with Griseofulvin and Dithane M-45 at 1000 ppm concentration and inhibited 42–67% mycelia growth of both fungal species

Table 2. Antifungal screening result of compounds 4a-l

Entry	Av % inhibition after 96 h against								
	<i>Fusarium oxisporum-udum</i>			<i>Alternaria solani</i>			<i>Aspergillus niger</i>		
	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm
4a	82	64	51	87	59	37	78	65	31
4b	84	60	41	80	56	32	74	65	32
4c	80	57	33	82	74	65	82	59	45
4d	100	90	63	99	78	69	100	86	65
4e	80	72	44	78	42	33	87	59	33
4f	82	69	46	80	65	48	79	61	45
4g	99	92	66	100	57	48	99	77	68
4h	83	61	39	82	60	42	85	65	46
4i	78	55	38	81	58	40	82	56	42
4j	84	68	46	80	64	47	79	59	39
4k	81	63	36	75	62	38	76	61	44
4l	100	82	62	99	81	68	100	84	71
Griseofulvin	100	94	90	100	95	91	100	96	92
Dithane M-45	100	90	85	100	96	90	100	97	91

even at the lowest concentration. The antifungal activity of the compounds varied upon the type and position of the substituent at 5-substituted-2-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazole moiety.

This demonstrates that the presence of hydrophilic group on phenyl amino ring (attached with position 2 of oxadiazole) enhances the antifungal activity while presence of hydrophobic group at same position decreases the antifungal activity. Compounds 4d, 4g and 4l in which hydrophilic group is present, exhibits activity of highest order.

Safety

Our objective was to find out a new general ecofriendly synthetic method for the preparation of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles in which the use of toxic and sensitive reagents could be minimized. Keeping these objectives in mind we have synthesized a large number of 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles at room temperature by electrochemical method in which energy input, use of hazardous chemicals and production of toxic wastes are reduced by using simple cell having platinum electrodes, safer solvents, supporting electrolyte, small amount of electricity as energy source. There is improvement of selectivity and shortening of reaction time. This principle also eliminates the complex isolation procedure and mechanical loss during the separation.

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